

Notes

Cadmium(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with some Bidentate Ligands

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COMPLEXES formed by metal(II) salts in solution with nicotinic acid, nicotinamide, isonicotinamide, 2- or 3-benzoylpyridine have received some attention¹ because of their biological importance. The present communication describes the

preparation and characterisation of compounds formed by the interaction of Cd²⁺ and Cu²⁺ chloride with nicotinic acid (NA), nicotinamide (NICA), isonicotinamide (INCA), 2- or 3-benzoylpyridine (2-BOP or 3-BOP).

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by reacting cadmium(II) and copper(II) chloride with the respective ligands in ethanol in 1 : 3 molar ratio. The products which precipitated immediately or crystallised out on standing were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes (Table I) were characterised by elemental, conductance (0.001 M in acetone), magnetic (room temperature), ir (nujol) and electronic spectral data.

TABLE I - ANALYTICAL AND IR DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)			Important ir bands			
	M	Cl	N	ν_{NH} Asym. (Sym.)	δ_{NH_2}	$\nu_{C=O}$	ν_{C-N}
[Cd(NA) ₂ Cl ₂]	26.02 (26.17)	16.21 (16.51)	6.31 (6.52)	-	-	-	-
[Cd(NICA) ₂ Cl ₂]	26.32 (26.29)	16.28 (16.58)	13.22 (13.10)	3 300 (3 180)	1 620	-	1 405
[Cd(INCA) ₂ Cl ₂]	26.15 (26.29)	16.82 (16.58)	13.28 (13.10)	3 310 (3 160)	1 630	-	1 410
[Cd(2-BOP) ₂ Cl ₂]	20.40 (20.50)	13.01 (12.90)	5.24 (5.09)	-	-	1 650	-
[Cd(3-BOP) ₂ Cl ₂]	20.49 (20.50)	12.72 (12.90)	5.19 (5.09)	-	-	1 655	-
[Cu(NA) ₂ Cl ₂]	16.09 (16.69)	18.82 (18.62)	6.92 (7.35)	-	-	-	-
[Cu(NICA) ₂ Cl ₂]	16.21 (16.77)	18.25 (18.72)	14.38 (14.78)	3 310 (3 140)	1 635	-	1 410
[Cu(INCA) ₂ Cl ₂]	16.34 (16.77)	16.36 (16.72)	14.46 (14.78)	3 320 (3 130)	1 640	-	1 415
[Cu(2-BOP) ₂ Cl ₂]	12.43 (12.69)	13.84 (14.16)	5.04 (5.59)	-	-	1 640	-
[Cu(3-BOP) ₂ Cl ₂]	12.21 (12.69)	13.75 (14.16)	5.21 (5.59)	-	-	1 645	-
(NA)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
(NICA)	-	-	-	3 380 (3 220)	1 605	-	1 390
(INCA)	-	-	-	3 370 (3 200)	1 615	-	1 385
(2-BOP)	-	-	-	-	-	1 670	-
(3-BOP)	-	-	-	-	-	1 680	-

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Results and Discussion

Low molar conductance values in acetone solution ($8-12 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate their non-electrolytic nature. The μ_{eff} values (1.86–1.99 B.M.) of the Cu^{2+} complexes correspond to the presence of the one unpaired electron. However no specific information regarding their stereochemistry² could be drawn from the magnetic moment data.

Electronic spectral bands at 15 385 and 18 870 cm^{-1} are observed in the spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, corresponding to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transition respectively, indicating³ square planar environment around Cu^{2+} . A single broad band centering around $\sim 15\,155 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are observed in the other Cu^{2+} complexes, indicating⁴ distorted octahedral geometries. From the ir spectra conductance and analysis we conclude that all the Cd^{2+} complexes are hexa-coordinated except the complex with nicotinic acid which is tetrahedral.

In nicotinic acid complexes the carboxyl vibration remains unchanged thus excluding the possibility of metal to oxygen coordination. However the pyridine part of the molecules exhibits appreciable shift. Bands around 1 580 and 1 550 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ modes, and pyridine ring vibration around 1 000, 990, 600 and 410 cm^{-1} indicate that coordination of the ligand takes place via pyridine ring nitrogen⁵. So the nicotinic acid acts and coordinates as monodentate ligand in the Cd^{2+} and Cu^{2+} complexes.

Infrared spectra of the nicotinamide and isonicotinamide complexes do not show any appreciable shift in the $\nu_{C=O}$ band but show considerable negative shifts (50–75 cm^{-1}) in case of ν_{NH} (asymmetric and symmetric) bands. The δ_{NH_2} mode of the ligands (1 605–1 615 cm^{-1}) reduced in intensity and shifted towards higher frequency side (1 620–1 640 cm^{-1}). However positive shift of pyridine ring vibration (10–15 cm^{-1}) are observed in the ir spectra of the complexes.

The significant shifts of the pyridine ring vibrations, ν_{NH} and δ_{NH_2} bands due to bonding of the nitrogen atoms clearly indicate⁶ the bidentate nature of the nicotinamide and isonicotinamide.

In 2-benzoylpyridine and 3-benzoylpyridine complexes, the ir spectra indicate a positive shift of pyridine ring vibration indicating the coordination through pyridine nitrogen to the ligands. The $\nu_{C=O}$ band of the ligands occurring at 1 680–1 670 cm^{-1} shifted to 1 650–1 640 cm^{-1} in the complexes, indicating⁷ coordination of carbonyl oxygen of the ligands to the metal ions. The non-ligand bands occurring at 520–510, 445–440 and 300–268 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to ν_{M-O} , ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-O_2} modes respectively⁸.

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Characterisation and X-Ray Diffraction Studies on $M(\text{bipyridyl})_2(\text{MoO}_4)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ Complexes with Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II)

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THE paper reports the structural study on the complexes of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} with 2,2'-bipyridyl formed in presence of MoO_4^{2-} oxoanion. Unit cell parameters have been calculated on the basis of X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the complexes.

Experimental

A mixture of powdered $\text{MMoO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Ni}/\text{Co}$) mixed with an aqueous solution of 2,2'-bipyridyl in 1 : 2 molar ratio was digested on a water-bath for 6–7 h. The solid material dissolved gradually to yield a clear solution which was evaporated till crystals (pink in case of Ni^{2+} , and orange in case of Co^{2+}) separated out. The crystals were filtered, washed 3–4 times with ethanol–water (80 : 20), recrystallised from water and dried (P_4O_{10}): Elemental analysis data : Ni^{2+} complex (Found : Ni, 9.98; N, 10.21; Mo, 17.0. $\text{Ni}(\text{bipy})_2(\text{MoO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires : N 10.20; Ni, 10.56; Mo, 17.48%). Co^{2+} complex (Found : Co, 10.01; N, 9.68; Mo,